

Employee Performance and Affecting Factors: An Application with Structural Equation Model

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-06, 2024, p. 223– 235 - 0099-0001-2406-0310.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS -

European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")
ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a

1

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI)
EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761
| RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-
353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")*

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ESRA DENİZ KAPLAN – University of Northwest
Master in Industrial Engineering
Orcid ID: 0009-0009-4502-0455
Mail: esradenizbalci@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research used structural equation modeling (SEM) to assess the correlations between various variables influencing employee performance in the Turkish pharmaceutical business, as well as the extent to which these factors impact performance.

Based on the information gathered from the literature, a comprehensive model was developed to analyze the factors influencing personal performance. This model consists of several independent and dependent variables, with intricate interrelationships among them. The examination of this sort of model has shown that SEM is the best suitable approach.

CURRENT SCIENCE

A linguistic variable-based survey was used as a technique for data gathering. The study was conducted among the workers and management of a pharmaceutical firm. The gathered data was transformed into linear data and quantified using the principles of fuzzy logic theory. The numerical data was examined using the SPSS software, and validity and reliability coefficients were calculated, confirming the dependability of the data.

The study is based on the theoretical framework of a structural equation model (SEM). An in-depth analysis has been conducted on the fundamental concepts of SEM, its evolution over time, and prior research on company success. The selection of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was contrasted

with other multivariate analytic techniques to determine the most suitable strategy for the thesis.

Conversely, fuzzy logic theory provides a mathematical structure for assessing performance in scenarios characterized by uncertainty and complexity. The primary emphasis of this chapter is on the theory of fuzzy sets, the process of constructing fuzzy sets, and the practical use of fuzzy numbers. The use of fuzzy logic theory is examined in relation to its ability to provide a more precise and complete assessment of performance in intricate commercial settings.

Keywords: Fuzzy logic theory, Performance, Structural Equation Model.

INTRODUCTION

This research uses analytical techniques, namely the structural equation model (SEM) and fuzzy logic theory, to examine the elements that influence human performance. This research is based on the examination of many viewpoints in the literature about the definition and measurement of the concept of performance. The thesis extensively analyzed the impact of human, institutional, and environmental variables on performance, which constituted its primary emphasis.

AIM

The primary objective of this research is to identify the elements that influence the individual performance of workers in the pharmaceutical sector and to analyze the impact of these factors on performance. This study, performed via field research on workers and their supervisors in the pharmaceutical business in Istanbul, seeks to assess the variables influencing the individual performance of individuals and investigate the impact of this performance on the overall success of the company. The objective is to gather the perspectives of the staff using a survey methodology, identify the system's

CURRENT SCIENCE

strengths and shortcomings, and collect data for the purpose of enhancing and advancing the system.

METHOD

The objective of the study is to identify the variables that influence the productivity of workers in the pharmaceutical sector and to examine the correlations among these variables. The study examined characteristics like personal motivation, business culture, leadership quality, collaboration, and environmental conditions. The impact of these factors on employee performance was analyzed via the use of structural equation modeling and fuzzy logic theory. The research population comprises diverse pharmaceutical enterprises functioning in Istanbul. The universe encompasses both multinational pharmaceutical corporations and firms of varying sizes, including medium-sized and small-sized enterprises. These firms are involved in the production, distribution, marketing, and other associated operations of pharmaceuticals. This study incorporates a sample group that has been selected using the random sampling technique. The sample comprises 25 female workers, 75 male employees, and randomly chosen supervisors of these employees from the population. The random sampling method is a selection technique that provides the researcher with an equal chance of being chosen for each person in the population. This approach enhances the external validity of the study and bolsters the generalizability of the findings. The workforce consists of 25 female workers and 75 male employees, together with their respective supervisors. These individuals are employed in different divisions across many organizations within the pharmaceutical sector in Istanbul. The primary methodology used in the process of gathering data is the utilization of a survey application. The survey form was created to assess the personal, institutional, and environmental elements identified in the literature study. The poll was sent to both workers and their supervisors. Participants were surveyed on their perspectives on topics including their work environment, levels of motivation, attitudes towards company culture, and the

CURRENT SCIENCE

impact of environmental variables on their job performance. The data was examined using SPSS, a program specifically designed for statistical analysis. The analytical procedure included conducting frequency distributions, calculating means and standard deviations, as well as doing numerous correlation studies. In addition, a structural equation model (SEM) was used to analyze the connections between the various components.

The Analysis Process was executed in the following manner:

Data Collection: The data was gathered by conducting a survey among participants employed in different pharmaceutical businesses operating in Istanbul. The survey was developed to assess demographic information, as well as personal, organizational, and environmental aspects.

Data Preparation: The gathered data was processed for analysis with SPSS software. An analysis of the data was conducted to investigate its fundamental properties, including frequency distributions, averages, standard deviations, and correlation analyses.

Model Development and Validation: A structural equation modeling (SEM) approach was used to construct a model that examines the correlations between demographic parameters such as gender, age, firm size, position, and working hours, and employee performance. The adequacy of the model was evaluated by using several fit indices, such as CFI, RMSEA, and Chi-square.

The use of fuzzy sets included the determination of membership functions to represent employee performance and demographic data. Membership ratings were used to quantify ambiguity and evaluate performance measures and demographic characteristics.

RESULTS

The ability and drive of a person have a significant role in determining their performance. Talent encompasses both inherent aptitudes and competencies acquired via formal education and practical experience (Özkalp, 1990). According to Bengiray

CURRENT SCIENCE

(1999), motivation is the factor that influences an individual's willingness and determination to accomplish their task at the required level.

Studies in the literature have shown that individuals' performances might undergo changes over time and fluctuate based on several aspects (Genç and Demirdöğen, 2000). Hence, it is crucial to consistently assess and oversee performance.

Approximately three-quarters of the participants are male (75%). This data illustrates the gender disparity within the pharmaceutical business, indicating that males are more prevalent in this field. The presence of women, being 25% of the sample, is enough for analyzing disparities in performance and motivation between genders. It is important to consider this disparity when examining the impact of gender on performance.

Upon analyzing the age group distribution, it becomes evident that the bulk of the participants fall between the 26-35 age range, accounting for 40% of the total. The next age bracket consists of those aged 36-45, accounting for 30% of the participants. It is crucial to comprehend the performance and motivation levels of the younger generation by considering the significant 15% representation of workers aged 18-25. The substantial proportion of individuals in the medium age group (26-45%) provides an opportunity to thoroughly investigate the impact of this age group on work performance. The underrepresentation of older workers (aged 46-55% and over 56) may result in a narrow assessment of the impact of these age groups on job performance.

45% of the participants are employed in large-scale organizations. 35% of the workforce is employed by medium-sized enterprises, whereas 20% of the workforce is employed by small-sized companies. This distribution provides a comprehensive viewpoint for analyzing the impact of firm size on employee performance. The experiences of workers in large-scale corporations provide crucial insights on the impact of company structure and resources on performance. The inclusion of medium- and small-sized organizations in the analysis allows for the comparison of employee performance across businesses of varying sizes.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Out of all the participants, 80% are workers, while managers make up 20%. This distribution serves as an appropriate foundation for studying disparities in the performance and motivation of workers and supervisors. The significant percentage of workers yields crucial data for comprehending the overall functioning of the workforce. A sample size of 20% of managers is enough to analyze the impact of leadership quality and management styles on employee performance.

Upon analyzing the distribution of working time, it becomes evident that the majority of participants possess 5 years or more of working experience, accounting for 35% of the total. The group of individuals with 3-5 years of work experience accounts for 30% of the total, while the group with 1-3 years of experience represents 25%. Lastly, the group with 0-1 year of experience makes up 10% of the total. This dataset offers a comprehensive range of information to assess the impact of work experience on employee performance. The substantial presence of personnel who have been with the company for an extended period of time (5 years or more) enables a thorough investigation of the impact of experience on performance. Analyzing the adaption process and early motives in the workplace is crucial by representing individuals with shorter-term tenure at a certain rate.

Approximately 55% of the workers exhibit a high or very high level of motivation. This indicates that work motivation is often maintained at a positive level. Nevertheless, there exists a subset of individuals comprising 15% who have a diminished level of drive.

It is observed that 50% of the participants have undergraduate degrees. The significant percentage of workers with advanced educational backgrounds indicates that organizations possess a highly skilled workforce.

According to the survey, 60% of workers said that they are able to use their abilities on a frequent or constant basis. This demonstrates the feasibility of using the necessary talents for the respective occupations. Nevertheless, 15% of respondents said that they seldom or never use their talents.

Approximately 60% of workers see the business culture in a favorable or very favorable manner. This demonstrates that the company maintains a favorable working

CURRENT SCIENCE

atmosphere. Nevertheless, 15% of respondents express a poor or very negative perception of the culture.

60% of respondents evaluated the quality of leadership and management as satisfactory or excellent. This indicates that managers are generally functioning well. Nevertheless, 15% of respondents said that the quality of management was subpar or very subpar, suggesting a need for improvement in leadership abilities in some domains.

Approximately 65% of workers said that the degree of cooperation and collaboration was assessed as good or very high. This demonstrates the robustness of cooperation and collaboration. Nevertheless, a significant proportion of 15% indicated insufficient levels of collaboration, highlighting the need to enhance cooperation in some domains. 60% of workers rated the physical characteristics of the working environment as satisfactory or excellent. This indicates that the physical working conditions are typically acceptable. Nevertheless, 15% of respondents assessed the working conditions as poor or really poor.

The influence of economic circumstances on employee performance is experienced at different levels. Seventy-five percent of the participants said that economic circumstances had a moderate or greater influence. This demonstrates that economic changes and financial stability have a significant impact on employee performance.

Seventy-five percent of the participants said that the competitive environment had a modest or greater impact on their performance.

Based on the participants' overall work performance appraisal, 50% of them reported being high or very high performers. This indicates that the overall performance level in enterprises is deemed adequate. Nevertheless, a notable 15% of individuals indicated subpar or very subpar performance, highlighting the need for implementing performance enhancement measures for some personnel.

Structural Equation Model (SEM)

CURRENT SCIENCE

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is used to elucidate the connections between observable variables and to explicate the intricate framework of these connections. This model was created to detect both direct and indirect relationships among several dependent and independent variables. SEM is sometimes described as a method of structural modeling that reflects observable variables.

SEM enables researchers to examine intricate linkages, assess the compatibility of the suggested theoretical model with the data, and adapt the model accordingly to get a comprehensive understanding of the complicated interconnections among variables. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a statistical technique used to evaluate pre-established theoretical models. A hypothesized structural model is used to define the connections between variables, and the data is evaluated to determine the degree to which this model accurately represents the data. SPSS provides a range of methods that facilitate the analysis of Structural Equation Modeling. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is used to assess the measurement model, whereas Structural Modeling (SEM) is utilized to analyze both the measurement model and the structural relationships simultaneously. Within this particular framework, the use of Structural Equation Model analysis offers the chance to comprehend and elucidate intricate connections. In our study, we opted for SPSS since it is a robust tool that simplifies these analyses and enables the presentation of data in a significant manner.

Evaluation and Interpretation of Findings

The research findings indicated substantial disparities in performance levels among male and female workers. Men had superior overall performance, whereas female workers demonstrated stronger performance in certain roles such as management.

Based on the examination of performance across different age groups, it was found that workers in the 26-35 age range had the greatest levels of performance. This discovery indicates that individuals in this age bracket are often at the peak of their professional lives, characterized by high levels of activity and productivity.

A study revealed that workers in large-scale organizations had superior performance compared to those in medium and small-sized companies. This scenario exemplifies

9

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI)
EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761
| RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-
353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

the beneficial impact of the resources and opportunities offered by major corporations on employee performance.

The study found that those in management roles had superior performance compared to those in employee jobs. This research corroborates the notion that managers bear more responsibility and exhibit higher levels of drive.

It was noted that there was a positive correlation between performance and working time. It was shown that workers who have worked for 5 years or more had the best levels of performance. This discovery illustrates the beneficial impact of experience on performance.

The research findings demonstrate the impact of environmental conditions and performance appraisal on workers' job performance. The performance of workers is significantly influenced by economic circumstances and the competitive environment. This scenario highlights the need for organizations to have strategic strategies to address economic uncertainty and competitive challenges.

Work-life balance support is a crucial component that directly impacts workers' effectiveness at work. Businesses may enhance their workers' work-life balance by providing additional assistance.

CONCLUSION

The research findings indicate that organizations should prioritize personal characteristics when developing their strategies for enhancing performance. Furthermore, it is crucial to enhance the working environment and optimize management techniques by considering institutional and environmental aspects.

RESTRICTION

There are some limitations encountered during the research. For example, factors such as participation rates and survey response accuracy during the data collection process

CURRENT SCIENCE

can affect the external validity of the research. In addition, the cross-sectional design of the research aims to describe the current situation and establish relationships rather than cause-effect relationships.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest with this article.

Financial Support: The author reports no use of financial support with this article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Current Science is a nationally based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this. The criteria of the Declaration of Helsinki were taken into account.

SOURCE

Akat, İ., & Üner, N. (1993). Business Management, 3rd Edition, Dokuz Eylül

University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, İzmir, 37-38.

Anastasi, A. (1990). Psychological Testing, 6th ed., Maxwell MacMillian

International Editions, New York, 13-46.

Ashgun, I. (1982). İşgören, 2nd Edition, Baytaş Publications, İstanbul, 104.

Ataay, D. (1987). Factors Affecting Manpower Efficiency in Businesses, 2nd Edition,

İstanbul University Faculty of Business Administration, Ankara, 235.

Carmines, E., & Zeller, R. (1982). Reliability and Validity Assessment, 5th ed.,

Beverly Hills: Sage Publications Inc., 182.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Cascio, W. (1992). *Managing Human Resources: Productivity, Quality of Work Life, Profits*, 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 127.
- Chen, S. (1997). "A new method for tool steel materials selection under fuzzy environment". *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 92, 265-274.
- Dubois, D., & Prade, H. (1983). "Ranking on fuzzy numbers in the setting of possibility theory". *Information Science*, 5, 121-126.
- Eren, E. (1984). *Management Psychology, Extended 2nd Edition*, Istanbul University Faculty of Economics Publications No.2, Istanbul,
- Frerichs, D., "An Analysis of a Preservice Teacher Structural Equation Model Under Varying Assumptions and Measurement Conditions", Doctoral Thesis, Iowa State University, Iowa (1989), pages 24-67.
- Shields, MD, "An Empirical Analysis of Firms' Implementation Experiences With Activity-Based Costing," *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 5: 148-166 (1993).